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Abstract

This work analyses how risk transference to the private partner affects the success of public-private partnerships (PPP). For this purpose, a broad sample from the World Bank database of 6,022 PPP infrastructure projects in 59 developing countries in the period 1997 to 2016 is analysed. Using multilevel logistic models our results show that PPPs' success is more likely when the private partner **takes more risk and the economic and institutional environments are better**. Another interesting finding is that an excessive transference of risks to the private party when certain institutional features show good records could prejudice PPPs' performance.

Keywords: public-private partnerships; risk transference; success; economic conditions; institutional environment; developing economies.

JEL Codes: G32, L32, L33

1. Introduction

Public-private partnerships (PPP) are defined by the Green Paper of the European Commission (2004, p. 3) as “forms of cooperation between public authorities and the world of business which aim to ensure the funding, construction, renovation, management or maintenance of an infrastructure or the provision of a service”. PPPs have been used, among others, for the provision of public infrastructure services in transport, energy, water and sewerage, or in the telecommunications sector (Jimenez et al., 2018); they are characterized by their long duration, the involvement of the private sector in different stages of the project (design, completion, implementation and funding), and the allocation of risks between the public and private partners (European Commission, 2004).

PPPs present several advantages that explain their rapid growth in recent decades. Firstly, the involvement of private companies in public procurement allows the harnessing of their skills, experience and technology innovation (Li et al., 2005), which could lead to improvements in the efficiency with which public assets are operated (Parker and Hartley, 2003; Edkins and Smyth, 2006). In addition, countries suffering from excessive public debt and facing budget constraints may use PPPs to attract private money for funding public services expansion (European Commission, 2004; Li et al., 2005).

Although this last advantage was initially the main driver for the use of PPPs, nowadays it is known that their real impact on public borrowing is more modest than at first supposed, and it is considered that their main advantage is as a mechanism that allows proper risk allocation between the public and private partners (Li et al., 2005), leading to relevant efficiency gains in the provision of public services (Hurst and Reeves, 2004). Jin and Zhang (2011) explain how risk allocation in PPPs differs from traditional public service procurement formulas: “In PPP projects, the government bears little or no asset-based risk

and is entitled to reducing payments, abatements and compensation if the service is not delivered to the specified standards” (p. 591). Specifically, Effah and Chan (2013) explain that the aim of PPPs is “to transfer design, construction, financial, commercial, operating and maintenance and other risks to the private sector, depending on the contractual arrangements, and to ensure value-for-money (VfM) through leveraging the management and technical skills of competent private sector firms” (p. 153). In this regard, authors such as Nisar (2007a) or Jin and Zhang (2011) point out that the main driver for achieving the best VfM in public projects is the transfer of risks to a private partner. The same conclusion is achieved by other researches performing case studies (Pollock et al., 2000; Froud and Shaoul, 2001; Shaoul, 2005; Nisar, 2007b).

For this reason, many articles in academic literature deal with risk allocation in PPPs projects. Most proceed in the same way: first they try to identify what relevant specific risk factors are affecting PPP projects; then they try to determine how these risk factors should be allocated to each party. To achieve these two aims, these papers usually distribute surveys among academicians and practitioners in order to collect their opinions according to their experience and expertise (see, among many others, Li et al., 2005; Chan et al., 2010; Ke et al., 2010; Hwang et al., 2013; Chou and Pramudawardhani, 2015). These papers offer valuable information that can be very useful when designing PPP contracts and, more specifically, when deciding the allocation of risks between the partners. However, there is no consensus on the risk allocation between the public and private parties (Hodge, 2004; Li et al., 2005; Ke et al., 2010; Marques and Berg, 2011). The opinions in the surveys could be biased by many factors (Thomas et al., 2003), and there is a lack of empirical studies of how the allocation between the parties really affects the PPP.

In terms of applied studies, Percoco (2014) analyses how this distribution of risk is influenced by the institutional environment where the PPP is deployed. Fleta et al. (2019) explore the determinants of the type of PPP used, each type presenting a different degree of risk transferred from the public sector to the private. Wang et al. (2019) examine how the allocation of risk affects the volume of private investment in PPP projects, and how the institutional environment affects this relationship. However, the literature does not analyse how risk transference to the private sector subsequently affects projects' success. Following Jiang et al. (2015) and Jimenez et al. (2017), we consider a successful project to be active, advanced or concluded. A failed project is one that is cancelled or distressed. Thus, the first research question (RQ) of this article is as follows:

RQ1: How does the level of risk transferred to the private sector affect PPPs' success?

In addition, since the success of PPP projects depends on environmental conditions, especially in developing economies (Yang et al., 2013), we analyse how economic and institutional frameworks (Queiroz, 2007) affect the success of the project. Although both aspects have previously been analysed, the different dimensions of the institutions, and the interaction of the environment with the risk transference, have not been researched. Thus, the following research questions arise:

RQ2: How does the economic environment affect PPPs' success?

RQ3: How does the economic environment affect the relationship between the level of risk transferred to the private sector and PPPs' success?

RQ4: How does the institutional environment affect PPPs' success?

RQ5: How does the institutional environment affect the relationship between the level of risk transferred to the private sector and PPPs' success?

To study all these matters, we examine a sample of 6,022 PPP infrastructure projects located in 59 developing countries in the period 1997–2016. As a methodological approach, we perform multilevel logistic models that allow us to control for the countries' specificities where projects are performed, providing more robust empirical evidence.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 shows the literature review and research hypotheses. Section 3 describes the data, variables and research methods used. Section 4 presents the empirical results and discussion. The paper ends with the main conclusions in section 5.

2. Literature Review and Research Hypotheses

2.1. Effect of Risk Transfer to Private Partner on PPPs' success

Risk factors arise from the uncertainty surrounding transactions, along with the limited rationality of the agents involved to anticipate them (Sanderson, 2012; Fleta-Asín and Muñoz, 2017). In the case of PPPs, the risks are shared in different forms and to different degrees. In this kind of agreement, another source of risk arises from the cooperation between the two partners (Parker and Hartley, 2003). This type of risk is generated by the bounded rationality of the agents (Simon, 1972) that creates information asymmetries and possible opportunistic behaviour among them (Williamson, 1979). These risks can appear *ex ante* through adverse selection (e.g. choice of a suboptimal private partner to perform the service)

(Akerlof, 1978), or *ex post* through moral hazard (e.g. poor performance or development related to the private parties' behaviour) (Holmstrom, 1979). The relevance of risk management is not only that it affects the efficiency of operations (Chou et al., 2012), but also that it can affect the success or failure of a project (Chou and Pramudawardhani, 2015).

The public party has several procedures to mitigate the risks mentioned. Firstly, it introduces a market mechanism to externalize the economic activity through a contracting procedure. The bidding system allows reduction of the adverse selection problem, since the private parties signal their interest in the offer (Spence, 2002) while the public party screens it twice: *ex ante* fixing the bidding conditions, and *ex dure* selecting the best offer during the process (Ismail et al., 2011; De Schepper et al., 2015). This mechanism also introduces significant competition into PPPs, which is important for efficiency and the consequent delivery of VfM (McQuaid and Scherrer, 2010, p. 29), because private bidders competing to get the project could provide innovative solutions to the lack of these competitive incentives, neglected under traditional public methods (Hurst and Reeves, 2004). Thus, these innovative solutions lead to enhanced quality and reduce operating expenses (Rangel and Galende, 2010).

Secondly, the public party establishes another procedure to diminish risks arising from moral hazard, assigning responsibility for the core activity of the agent in charge through incentives and/or penalties (Williamson, 1979; Jin and Zhang, 2011). Several researches document the benefits of this practice (Mathur and Banchuenvijit, 2007), especially in developing economies (Leigland, 2018). Thus, the previous academic literature has found that the involvement of a private contractor in public procurement leads to gains in operational efficiency in different sectors such as water (Gassner et al., 2009; Marin, 2009), electricity (Gassner et al., 2009; Andrés et al. 2013), transportation (Perelman and Serebrisky,

2010), telecommunication (Estache and Rossi, 2004; Andrés et al. 2013) or specific activities as management of ports (Wanke and Barros, 2015).

Additionally, in the PPP design process, the public party has an incentive to transfer the economic activity and its risks to a greater extent than simply those emerging from the core activity (Thomas et al., 2003; Ng and Loosemore, 2007). This incentive occurs because of the indivisibilities and interrelationships with other core activities, as well as the protracted time of use of the asset or service by other agents (Hart, 2003). The fact that the public party entrusts the integral economic activity to the private party generates a temporary allocation of property rights with respect to those activities that may be affected by their economic activity, which can also include residual property rights in case part of the ownership is transferred (Grossman and Hart, 1986; Hart and Moore, 1990; Blanc-Brude et al., 2007). This causes that private party has incentives to perform efficiently, reducing costs of supervision and hidden defects usually assumed by the public party (Lyons et al., 2007). Thus, the public side could use its own resources less, focusing on its fundamental competencies (Felsing, 2011), diversifying the risks more, and achieving higher efficiency because the moral hazard decreases to a higher degree (Brinkerhoff and Brinkerhoff, 2011).

Public party could promote a specific type of PPP to transfer higher risks to the private party (Jin and Doloi, 2008; Fleta et al., 2019): the *ex ante* acceptance of risk by the private party will reveal its capability to assume and manage risk better by signalling itself as a candidate in the tendering process (Nisar, 2007a; Effah and Chan, 2013). Private acceptance of risk would guarantee the greater efficiency and success of the project, because this acceptance means that the private partner considers that the cost-benefit analysis of the risk assumed is positive (Jin and Zhang, 2011; Effah and Chan, 2013). For instance, if the same private contractor in charge of the asset construction also takes responsibility for maintaining

and/or subsequently operating the asset (Hart (2003), this private company has an incentive to build the asset according to quality standards, since anything else could lead to higher costs and financial penalties for the duration of the PPP (Nisar, 2007a). In this way, bundling responsibilities in the private contractor could enhance the scope for efficiency gains (Allen, 2001).

Thus, we propose the following research hypothesis.

H1: The higher the risks transferred to the private contractor, the greater the likelihood of PPP success.

2.2. Effect of Economic Environment

Economic conditions are highlighted by academicians and practitioners when they are questioned about the most relevant risks factors for PPPs' success, since the difficulties of operating in unfavourable environments are high. As several authors point out, one of the key factors in implementing successful PPPs is a stable macroeconomic environment (Sharma, 2012; Chou and Pramudawardhani, 2015; Cui et al., 2018), which is less prevalent in developing countries (Yang et al., 2013). Li et al. (2005) mention specific macroeconomic risk factors encompassing poor financial market, inflation rate volatility, interest rate volatility and influential economic events. Ke et al. (2010, p. 486) identify a further financial risk in unavailability of financial instruments, which can provoke a higher finance cost (Hwang et al., 2013).

Macroeconomic conditions also have an impact on the way in which governments procure infrastructures. More concretely, a weak economic environment has a negative impact on the use of PPPs. Ettinger et al. (2005) explain that the peak of PPPs in infrastructure

projects located in developing countries occurred in 1997/1998, and several factors thereafter led to a significant fall in the number of these projects and the amount of money managed by them, highlighting the 1997/1998 crisis. Other reasons for this evolution were (“the bursting of the dot-com and telecommunications bubbles, and the slowdown in world economic growth, which reduced the demand for new infrastructure and the price investors were willing to pay at auctions” (Ettinger et al., 2005, p.3). Loxley (2012) analyses how changes in financial and insurance markets triggered by financial crises affect private sector involvement in PPP projects. The author finds that the reaction of the private sector to these changes is characterized by: i) restructuring PPP financing; ii) brusquely reducing PPP activity; and iii) lobbying governments to achieve financial help. Burger et al. (2009) point out that the main channels through which financial crises affect PPP projects are cost and access to finance. In crisis times, financial institutions prefer to grant short-term instead of long-term loans. This negatively affects the involvement of the private sector in PPP infrastructure projects, since it experiences problems accessing the funding required for these projects.

On the other hand, there are microeconomic conditions which can also affect the success of PPPs. These conditions are related to the quantity and quality of the productive factors where the PPPs are located (Fleta et al., 2019), which usually present poorer conditions in developing countries (Dunning and Lundan, 2008; Porter and Schaw, 2008; Ramírez-Alesón and Fleta-Asín, 2016). In fact, numerous risk factors related to productive factor endowments are identified in PPP literature, such as the availability of material and labour (Xu et al., 2011), design deficiencies (Hurst and Reeves, 2004; Shen et al., 2006), implementation delays (Shen et al., 2006; Chou et al., 2012), low productivity of designated operations (Li et al., 2005; Chan et al., 2010), maintenance more expensive than expected (Thomas et al.,

2003; Marques and Berg, 2011), cost overrun (Thomas et al., 2003; Shen et al., 2006; Chou et al., 2012) or delay in supply (Chou et al., 2012; Chou and Pramudawardhani, 2015).

In addition, when improvement of the economic environment occurs before the bidding process, it favours private interest, increasing the number of bidders and competition, facilitating efficiency gains and greater risk-taking (Martin and Scott, 2000). On the other hand, when the private party supports greater activities and risk, an improvement in economic conditions will imply greater benefits, because the activities affected in a positive way are more extensive. Furthermore, these private partners may devote a greater number of resources and effort to control other risks, favouring success. That is why PPPs where the private partner assumes a higher degree of risk could benefit from favourable economic environments to carry out their collaboration successfully.

These arguments lead us to propose the next research hypotheses.

H2a: More favourable economic environments positively affect the likelihood of PPPs' success.

H2b: The positive effect on PPPs' success of transferring risks to the private sector is intensified under more favourable economic environments.

2.3. Effect of Institutional Environment

The institutional environment is another relevant source of uncertainty that could affect PPPs' performance (Fleta et al., 2019). Yang et al. (2013) highlight that institutional uncertainty is one of the main problems for PPPs' development in transitional economies. Such uncertainty can be seen in different risk factors. Hwang et al. (2013) identify some of

them as lack of support of the government, the existence of an unstable government, the risk of nationalization or expropriation, the existence of strong political interference, or corruption and bribery practices. Emirullah and Azam (2014) find that regulatory quality and government effectiveness positively affect PPPs' performance in the specific case of ASEAN (Association of Southeast Asian Nations) countries. Panayides et al. (2015) conclude that in the case of ports' infrastructures, the regulatory quality and the ease of enforcing contracts are important factors for PPPs' success. Wang et al. (2019) point out that the governance environment, encompassing factors such as political stability or the quality of regulations, is an important determinant of the volume of investment of private companies in PPP projects. In the same way, Mota and Moreira (2015) point out that the sustainability of PPPs is related to the quality of institutions.

Among all these institutional factors, corruption is one of the most studied. Cuervo-Cazurra (2006, p. 808) defines it as "the exercise of public power for private gain". Corruption appears "whenever a public official has discretionary power over distribution to the private sector of a benefit or cost" (Rose-Ackerman, 1997, p. 31). Jimenez et al. (2017) analyse the impact of corruption on PPP performance in Central and Eastern European countries, finding that higher levels of host-country corruption are negatively related to PPP success. Castro et al. (2014) conclude that greater corruption in the area where the infrastructure provision occurs is linked to lower efficiency in public contract execution. Thus, inefficiencies in traditional public procurement methods could be especially relevant when the public sector is characterized by high levels of corruption. In this way, O'Toole and Tarp (2014) find that corruption reduces the efficiency of capital investment. In the same vein, Guccio et al. (2019) find that in more corrupt environments, public officers show fewer incentives to monitor contract enforcements, leading to overruns and delays. More

specifically, these authors point out that “the purchasing officer is less accountable and has less incentives to carry on his monitoring activity” (p. 16).

However, corruption is not the only relevant characteristic of the institutional framework affecting PPPs’ development (Guccio et al., 2019). Bandiera et al. (2009) distinguish between inefficiencies sourced from defects in the regulatory system (passive waste, which does not benefit rent-seeking public officials) and inefficiencies sourced from corruption that benefits public managers. The authors find that in the case of Italy, the first type has a higher impact. Pongsiri (2002) analyses the impact of regulation in PPP projects, finding that a good regulatory framework enhances the efficiency of the public sector and attracts private investors, since it provides them with additional guarantees. Pessoa (2010) points out that developing economies are characterized by a lack of institutional capacity, weak governance systems, and unclear or unsuitable rules and regulations, all these factors leading to higher transaction costs and risk, making it more difficult to perform PPP projects successfully in these environments. More recently, Percoco (2014) finds that a more robust institutional environment has a positive effect on risk allocation to the private partner in the specific case of the transportation sector. More specifically, the author documents that better records on institutional aspects such as political and civil rights, rule of law and quality of the regulatory environment “are important determinants of the willingness of private parties to participate in PPP-type investment” (Percoco, 2014, p. 54).

This reasoning leads us to propose the next two research hypotheses.

H3a: A more favourable institutional environment positively affects the likelihood of PPPs’ success.

H3b: The positive effect on PPPs’ success of transferring risk to the private sector is intensified under more favourable institutional environments.

Thus, Figure 1 shows the hypotheses proposed: the effect on PPP success of risk transference (H1), and economic (H2a) and institutional environments (H3a); as well as the impact on projects’ success of the interaction effect between risk transference and the economic (H2b) and institutional environments (H3b).

Figure 1: Research hypotheses

3. Variables, Data and Research Method

3.1. Dependent Variable: Success or Failure of PPPs

We analyse the effect on PPPs' performance of risk transfer to the private sector. Our main data source is the World Bank's Private Participation in Infrastructure database (WBPD). This source is publicly available and its use in PPP academic research is widespread (see, among many others, Jimenez et al., 2018; Fleta et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2019). The database provides information about project status in terms of five different states: cancelled, distressed, advanced, active and concluding. In order to approach project success or failure, and following Jiang et al. (2015) and Jimenez et al. (2017), we build a binary variable (Success) from the project status information, coded 1 (successful) when the project status is advanced, active or concluding and 0 (failure) when the project status is cancelled or distressed.

3.2. Independent Variables

Our first research hypothesis (H1) proposes that a higher risk transfer to a private partner is positively associated with a greater likelihood of project success. In order to approach the level of risk transferred to the private sector, and following previous literature (see, among others, Percoco, 2014; Zhang, 2014; Fleta et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2019), we use the variable from the World Bank's Private Participation in Infrastructure database **labelling** the subtype. PPP projects are classified by the World Bank in four main types—management and lease contracts, brownfield projects, greenfield projects and divestiture projects—which are, in turn, divided into twelve categories as follows: management contract; lease contract; rehabilitate, operate and transfer; rehabilitate, lease or rent and transfer; build, rehabilitate, operate and transfer; build, lease and transfer; build, operate and transfer; build, own and operate; merchant; rental; partial divestiture; and full divestiture. Each of these labels represents a category of PPP contract, ranked from less to more risk transferred from the public to the private sector, according to the World Bank.

Following previous literature, we create a risk ranking index (Risk) from this information (Percoco, 2014; Wang et al., 2019). The risk variable can adopt values in the range from 1 to 12 for each of the projects in the sample, according to the category label for that project and respecting the order established by the World Bank database (Figure 2). Thus, lower (higher) values for this indicator represent a lower (higher) degree of risk transferred to the private partner. For example, if we take the extreme forms of PPP according to this classification, if the project in the sample is categorized as a management contract (the first category, for which risk would adopt a value of 1), the private contractor only assumes the risk of managing a public asset in a period spanning between three and five years; however, when the project is labelled as full divestiture (the twelfth category, for which risk would adopt the value of 12), the government will transfer all the risk to the private sector, none remaining on the public side. This proxy for risk shows the risk allocation from a macro perspective according to the category of PPP contract and presents an important advantage, since it allows risk allocation comparisons among PPP projects, which in turn allows large samples to be analysed (Wang et al., 2019).

Figure 2: Risk-ranking index

Source: elaborated according to World Bank’s private participation in infrastructure Database (WBPD) criteria. In World Bank’s website, the reader can find a detailed definition of each category.

In order to test hypothesis 2a, the economic environment is approached by the degree of development of the country where the PPP is located. The degree of development (Dev) is measured by the log of the GDP per capita, following Balassa (1985) and Mota and Moreira (2015), among others. In fact, the log of GDP per capita has previously been used in literature to approach favourable economic conditions for transactions in PPPs (Albalade et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2018). As Fleta et al. (2019) explain, since several variables representing economic environment could be highly correlated (macroeconomic stability, endowment of basic infrastructures, etc.), the use of one proxy for all these factors saves potential multicollinearity problems and makes the interpretation of empirical evidence easier (Svensson, 1998; Ramírez-Alesón & Fleta-Asín, 2016). Following prior literature, we obtain the log of GDP per capita for each country where the PPP is located, according to the year before the project was established. In order to test H2b, we interact the risk variable with the log of GDP per capita.

In order to test hypothesis 3a, we use the variables from the World Bank's Worldwide Governance Indicators database (WGI). This information is publicly available and has been used previously in PPP literature to approach institutional environment quality (Percoco, 2014; Baker, 2016; Wang et al., 2019). The WGI database is composed of six indicators covering different issues: control of corruption (CC), government effectiveness (GE), political stability and absence of violence (PS), regulatory quality (RQ), rule of law (RL) and voice and accountability (VA). All can be downloaded from the World Bank and range from approximately -2.5 to 2.5, with higher values representing better outcomes.

Kauffman (2011, p. 4) defines each of these indicators. The control of corruption indicator shows "perceptions of the extent to which public power is exercised for private gain, including both petty and grand forms of corruption, as well as 'capture' of the state by elites and private interests". Government effectiveness is defined as: "perceptions of the quality of public services, the quality of the civil service and the degree of its independence from political pressures, the quality of policy formulation and implementation, and the credibility of the government's commitment to such policies". Political stability and the absence of violence is the "perception of the likelihood that the government will be destabilized or overthrown by unconstitutional or violent means, including politically-motivated violence and terrorism". Regulatory quality represents "the ability of the government to formulate and implement sound policies and regulations that permit and promote private sector development". The rule of law covers "the extent to which agents have confidence in and abide by the rules of society, and in particular the quality of contract enforcement, property rights, the police, and the courts, as well as the likelihood of crime and violence". Finally, voice and accountability refers to "the extent to which a country's citizens are able to participate in selecting their government, as well as freedom of expression,

freedom of association, and a free media”. All these variables are lagged one year from the project start, as in the case of Dev. Finally, to test hypothesis 3b, we created interaction variables by multiplying the risk variable with each of the WGI indicators.

In addition, we consider several control variables at both the project and country levels. First, at project level, we control for the activity sector. The projects in the sample analysed are allocated by the World Bank to either the energy, transport, information and communication technology (ICT), or water and sewerage activity sector. Each sector has special characteristics that could affect the topic under study in the paper (Cui et al., 2018). Thus, we create three dummy variables, *d_Energy*, *d_Transport* and *d_ICT*, adopting the value of 1 when the project belongs to the energy, transport or ICT sectors, and 0 otherwise. We take as our base category the water and sewerage sector, excluding it from the model in order to avoid perfect multicollinearity. We also consider the size and age of the project, since these could affect the PPP project success and risk transfer to the private sector (Jiang et al., 2015; Jimenez et al., 2017). This information it is also obtained from the World Bank database. The size of the project (*Size*) is approached by the log of total investment in millions of US dollars (USD). The age of the project (*Age*) is computed as the difference between the year when the project started and the last year with information for this project in the database. In addition, and following Fleta et al. (2019), since some PPPs are set out in different years, we include time control variables from 1999 (the first year with enough observations) in five-year units: *d1999*, *d2004*, *d2009* and *d2014*. These dummy variables adopt the value of 1 where the project was established in that year, and 0 otherwise. Furthermore, we consider the presence of local investors in the project. Thus, we include a dummy variable (*Local*) that adopts the value of 1 where there is at least one local company among private sponsors of the PPP, and 0 otherwise.

At country-level, we include the log of GDP (GDP) and the Polconv index (Polconv) (Henisz, 2002) following previous literature (Jimenez et al., 2017). The Polconv index allows us to control for the political stability of the country where the PPP occurs. In addition, we include dummy variables to control for the continent where the country is located. Thus, we add the variables *d_Africa*, *d_America* and *d_Asia* that adopt the value of 1 where the country is located in Africa, America or Asia respectively, and 0 otherwise. Europe is taken as the base category and is not considered in the specification to avoid perfect multicollinearity.

3.3. Data Set and Summary Statistics

Our main data source is the World Bank's Private Participation in Infrastructure database. From this source, we obtain information about the project variables in the models: Success, Risk, *d_Energy*, *d_Transport*, *d_ICT*, Size, Age, *d1999*, *d2004*, *d2009*, *d2014*, Local, *d_Africa*, *d_Asia* and *d_America*. The proxies for institutional environment—CC, GE, PS, RQ, RL and VA—are obtained from the WGI. GDP and Dev are also obtained from the World Bank. Finally, the Polconv index is collected from the Wharton University website (Henisz, 2002).

In total, the sample comprises 6,022 PPP projects from 59 developing countries in the period 1997–2016. The sample is determined by data availability. We have included in the models testing the research hypotheses all projects with records of the variables. The country with the highest number of PPPs is Brazil (1,310 projects), while the average number of projects per country is 102. Figure 3 presents the geographical distribution of projects in our sample. Table 1 provides the summary statistics of the variables included in our models, and Table 2 presents the correlation matrix for these variables.

Figure 3: Number of PPPs per country from 1997-2016

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of the data*.

Variable	Label	Median	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Success	Succes	1	0.957	0.204	0	1
Energy Sector	d_Energy	0	0.432	0.495	0	1
Transport Sector	d_Transport	0	0.177	0.382	0	1
ICT Sector	d_ITC	0	0.303	0.460	0	1
1999 year	d1999	0	0.046	0.209	0	1
2004 year	d2004	0	0.054	0.226	0	1
2009 year	d2009	0	0.072	0.259	0	1
2014 year	d2014	0	0.055	0.229	0	1
Africa	d_Africa	0	0.063	0.243	0	1
America	d_America	0	0.421	0.494	0	1
Asia	d_Asia	0	0.432	0.495	0	1
Log of total investment	Size	4.343	4.300	1.641	-3.507	10.480
Contract age	Age	10	10.531	4.686	2	21
Presence of local Sponsor	Local	1	0.583	0.493	0	1
GDP (log)	GDP	27.418	26.801	1.913	19.865	29.981
Polconv	Polconv	0.682	0.471	0.312	0.000	0.858
Risk ranking index	Risk	8	7.471	2.322	1.000	12.000
GDP per capita (log)	Dev	8.142	7.990	1.009	5.218	9.681
Control of corruption	CC	-0.398	-0.400	0.354	-1.638	0.809
Government effectiveness	GE	-0.095	-0.165	0.329	-1.719	0.644
Political Stability	PS	-0.522	-0.617	0.607	-3.181	0.978
Regulatory Quality	RQ	-0.201	-0.168	0.421	-2.133	0.871
Rule of Law	RL	-0.388	-0.384	0.381	-1.897	0.464
Voice and Accountability	VA	0.114	-0.228	0.799	-2.250	0.786

* All the variables contain 6,022 observations

Table 2. Correlation Matrix (part I)*.

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1. Success											
2. d_Energy	-0.037										
3. d_Transport	-0.010	-0.404									
4. d_ITC	0.041	-0.576	-0.306								
5. d1999	-0.105	-0.033	-0.018	0.061							
6. d2004	-0.018	-0.045	-0.038	0.053	-0.052						
7. d2009	0.025	0.009	-0.027	0.015	-0.061	-0.067					
8. d2014	0.044	0.040	-0.009	-0.029	-0.053	-0.058	-0.068				
9. d_Africa	-0.009	-0.129	-0.076	0.245	0.012	0.002	0.028	-0.006			
10. d_America	-0.089	0.121	-0.033	-0.044	0.086	0.019	0.005	0.038	-0.222		
11. d_Asia	0.069	0.007	0.132	-0.217	-0.092	-0.023	-0.026	-0.013	-0.226	-0.744	
12. Size	0.040	-0.052	0.115	0.119	-0.068	-0.094	0.027	0.073	-0.025	0.063	-0.062
13. Age	-0.142	-0.153	-0.020	0.161	0.396	0.177	-0.091	-0.337	-0.012	0.079	-0.097
14. Local	0.076	0.084	0.225	-0.326	-0.067	-0.011	-0.002	-0.002	-0.235	-0.164	0.270
15. GDP	0.133	0.201	0.138	-0.468	-0.087	-0.079	0.008	0.093	-0.462	0.022	0.264
16. Polconv	0.009	0.097	0.134	-0.052	0.038	-0.018	0.023	0.033	-0.171	0.335	-0.283
17. Risk	0.078	-0.067	-0.435	0.585	0.048	-0.003	0.038	0.003	0.141	-0.081	-0.128
18. Dev	0.032	0.179	-0.091	-0.120	-0.056	-0.129	0.078	0.173	-0.279	0.574	-0.489
19. CC	0.036	0.205	0.065	-0.267	0.057	0.036	0.006	0.035	-0.130	0.502	-0.203
20. GE	0.016	0.158	0.111	-0.348	0.052	0.015	-0.017	0.038	-0.225	0.167	0.140
21. PS	-0.039	0.114	-0.109	-0.074	0.042	-0.012	-0.007	-0.009	0.016	0.390	-0.394
22. RQ	0.082	0.119	0.040	-0.175	0.126	-0.017	-0.021	0.045	-0.101	0.494	-0.344
23. RL	0.037	0.143	0.190	-0.275	0.056	-0.052	-0.040	0.054	-0.052	0.050	0.183
24. VA	-0.055	0.096	0.149	-0.040	0.047	-0.016	0.019	0.023	-0.096	0.552	-0.427
VIF	-	4.15	2.99	5.25	1.12	1.04	1.04	1.15	2.06	4.04	5.09

*In bold, it is highlighted the correlations significant at 10%.

Table 2. Correlation Matrix (part II)*.

Variable	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
13. Age	-0.207												
14. Local	-0.030	-0.088											
15. GDP	0.099	-0.248	0.493										
16. Polconv	0.234	-0.079	0.158	0.173									
17. Risk	0.164	0.052	-0.263	-0.334	-0.028								
18. Dev	0.170	-0.371	0.023	0.362	0.180	-0.077							
19. CC	0.061	0.032	0.098	0.311	0.334	-0.228	0.401						
20. GE	0.050	-0.034	0.282	0.544	0.172	-0.244	0.307	0.658					
21. PS	-0.118	0.099	-0.109	-0.009	-0.014	-0.098	0.392	0.403	0.215				
22. RQ	0.097	0.057	0.038	0.226	0.304	-0.097	0.485	0.672	0.672	0.285			
23. RL	0.137	-0.085	0.249	0.352	0.472	-0.208	0.064	0.688	0.670	0.141	0.502		
24. VA	0.214	-0.036	0.051	0.048	0.803	-0.067	0.216	0.501	0.256	0.071	0.411	0.549	
VIF	1.26	1.92	1.47	2.39	1.47	1.94	3.35	1.90	1.72	1.33	1.54	2.02	4.29

*In bold, it is highlighted the correlations significant at 10%.

3.4. Statistical Estimation Technique: Multilevel Models

Since the dependent variable has a binary nature (0 = failure; 1 = success), we use a logistic regression to test the research hypotheses proposed in section 2 (Cameron and Trivedi, 2010; Jimenez et al., 2018). We also use multilevel models to control for the hierarchical structure of our data (Hox, 1998), considering that projects are nested in countries (Fleta et al., 2019). Multilevel models allow us to control for the specificities that could be present in each country. In addition, in all the models where interaction terms appear, we use mean-centred variables to avoid multicollinearity problems (Aiken and West, 1991).

Following the academic literature, we first create a base model with the control variables, and subsequently we add the proxies gradually to test the research hypotheses (Oxley, 1999; Lu and Beamish, 2001; Brouthers et al., 2008). This procedure is commonly used in public-private partnership (PPP) research (De Schepper et al., 2015; Wang and Ma, 2019). It allows us to check whether the signs and significance are consistent across models. The base model including all the control variables, where the sub index ‘i’ represents each observation and ‘u’ is the error term, is as follows (Model 1):

$$\begin{aligned} Success_i = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 d_Energy_i + \beta_2 d_Transport_i + \beta_3 d_ICT_i + \beta_4 d1999_i + \beta_5 d2004_i \\ & + \beta_6 d2009_i + \beta_7 d2014_i + \beta_8 Size_i + \beta_9 Age_i + \beta_{10} Local_i + \beta_{11} GDP_i \\ & + \beta_{12} Polconv_i + u_i \end{aligned}$$

To test hypothesis 1, we add to the base model the risk ranking index (Risk) (Model 2), as follows:

$$Success_i = Base\ Model + \beta_{13} Risk_i + u_i$$

To test hypotheses 2a and 2b, we add to Model 2 the log of the GDP per capita (*Dev*) (Model 3) and its interaction with the risk ranking index (*Risk*) (Model 4), as follows:

$$Success_i = BaseModel + \beta_{13}Risk_i + \beta_{14}Dev_i + u_i$$

$$Success_i = BaseModel + \beta_{13}Risk_i + \beta_{14}Dev_i + \beta_{15}Risk_i * Dev_i + u_i$$

To test hypothesis 3a, we run several models built by adding to Model 2 each of the variables from WGI. Following previous literature (Percoco, 2014; Wang et al., 2019), we add each of the six governance indicator variables to Model 2 separately in order to avoid possible multicollinearity problems due to the high correlations between each pair (see Table 2) (Models 5–10):

$$Success_i = Base Model + \beta_{13}Risk_i + \beta_{14}WGI_i + u_i$$

Finally, to test hypothesis 3b, we add to Model 2 one by one the proxies for the institutional environment (WGI) and their interaction with the risk ranking index (*Risk*) (Models 11–16):

$$Success_i = Base Model + \beta_{13}Risk_i + \beta_{14}WGI_i + \beta_{15}Risk_i * WGI_i + u_i$$

4. Empirical Results and Discussion

4.1. Main findings

Table 3 shows the results from the estimations for the base model (Model 1) and for the models testing H1 (Model 2), H2a (Model 3) and H2b (Model 4). The coefficients reported represent the log odds; in brackets, we can observe the standard errors for the estimated coefficients. Thus, in Model 1, for example, the coefficient on the *Polconv* variable means that for every one unit increase in this variable, we could expect a 1.776 increase in the log

odds of PPP success, if the rest of the variables are held constant. The odds ratio of success would be the quotient between the likelihood of success and of failure. For the four models, we can observe that the likelihood ratio χ^2 reaches p-values below 0.01, showing that all the models are statistically significant. Furthermore, the likelihood ratio comparing the nested model also indicates that to cluster PPPs in countries fits better. In addition, since the VIF (variance inflation factor) shows values from 2.23 to 2.44 in the four models, less than the limit of 10 suggested by Kennedy (1992) and Studenmund and Cassidy (1992) and the stricter limit of 5.3 proposed by Hair et al. (1998), there are no multicollinearity problems.

With regard to the control variables, we can observe that, in general terms, the success of PPP projects depends negatively on size and age and is positively associated with the GDP, Polconv and local variables. This means that projects that are smaller, younger and involve local private firms, and that are located in countries with a higher GDP and with more political stability, present a higher likelihood of success. All these results are consistent with previous literature. The results for size are in line with those previously found by Jimenez et al. (2017), who explain that projects with a greater size are more complex and difficult to manage, and consequently the likelihood of failure for these projects is higher. The results for age are consistent with those obtained by Jiang et al. (2015), who also document a negative and significant relationship between the success of the project and its age.

Jiang et al. (2015, p. 298) explain that there could be a failure bias for more recent projects and that “newly privatized projects, although still under construction now, may have problems in the future given enough time of observation”. The positive coefficient on the local variable indicates that the participation of local private sponsors in PPPs favours the success of the project. In this regard, Jimenez et al. (2017) find that the presence of local investors in PPP projects moderates the negative effect of corruption on PPPs’ performance,

since local investors know better the characteristics of the host country where the project is performed and “this higher familiarity with the host-country idiosyncrasy reduces the liability of foreignness limitations suffered by the rest of the firms in the project” (Jimenez et al., 2017, p. 788). With regard to the dummies for activity sectors, it seems that the likelihood of success is especially important in the case of ICT projects. Jiang et al. (2015) and Jimenez et al. (2018) obtain similar empirical evidence. The positive relationship between the success of the PPP and the log GDP of the host country has been previously documented by Jimenez et al. (2018), while the positive coefficient on the Polconv variable indicates that the likelihood of PPP success is greater when the project is located in countries with low levels of political risk (Jiang et al., 2015; Jimenez et al., 2017). Results for years and continents dummies are not reported in all the models for the sake of brevity, but they can be requested from the authors.

Focusing on the research hypotheses results, hypothesis 1 is tested in Model 2. We can observe that the coefficient on Risk is positive and significant ($\beta_{13} = 0.223$), meaning that a greater transference of risk to a private party leads to a higher likelihood of PPPs’ success. As explained in introduction and literature review and research hypotheses sections, the main benefit for PPPs is obtained from risk transfer to the private sector (Hodge, 2004; Nisar, 2007a; McQuaid and Scherrer, 2010) thanks to the efficiency gains achieved from the incentives generated by the tendering process. These improvements in efficiency could have a greater scope as more responsibilities are bundled in the private sector (Allen, 2001; Hart, 2003; Nisar, 2007a). Our results link the efficiency gains from transferring risks to private partners previously documented in academic literature with PPPs’ performance. We can conclude that as more responsibilities are bundled on the private partner, it is more likely that PPP projects will succeed. Thus, we cannot reject H1.

Table 3. Multilevel logistic analysis: PPPs success as the dependent variable. Base model, risk-transfer and economic environment.

<i>Hypotheses Variables</i>	Model 1	Model 2 (H1)	Model 3 (H2a)	Model 4 (H2b)
Risk (H1)		0.223*** (0.048)	0.226*** (0.048)	0.259*** (0.050)
Dev (H2a)			0.536** (0.265)	0.582** (0.265)
Risk*Dev (H2b)				0.139*** (0.038)
<i>Control Variables</i>				
d_Energy	0.738** (0.337)	0.261 (0.356)	0.274 (0.355)	0.355 (0.359)
d_Transport	0.429 (0.358)	0.496 (0.363)	0.505 (0.362)	0.490 (0.362)
d_ITC	2.216*** (0.265)	1.331*** (0.419)	1.346*** (0.419)	1.358*** (0.421)
Size	-0.074 (0.052)	-0.120** (0.054)	-0.135** (0.055)	-0.164*** (0.056)
Age	-0.082*** (0.022)	-0.084*** (0.022)	-0.060** (0.025)	-0.058** (0.025)
Local	0.460** (0.180)	0.487*** (0.183)	0.499*** (0.182)	0.518*** (0.184)
GDP	0.281** (0.134)	0.315** (0.137)	0.154 (0.163)	0.160 (0.160)
Polconv	1.776*** (0.572)	1.674*** (0.579)	1.406** (0.586)	1.502** (0.586)
Time	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Continent	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Intercept	-3.325 (3.485)	-5.136 (3.555)	-5.584 (3.662)	0.214 (4.104)
Random parameter	2.199 (0.721)	2.329 (0.768)	2.255 (0.754)	2.099 (0.704)
Wald χ^2	135.76***	148.58***	152.69***	151.80***
LR test vs. Logit	354.76***	332.76***	336.70***	321.25***
Observations	6,022	6,022	6,022	6,022
Pseudo R ²	0.5431	0.5523	0.5541	0.5638
VIF	2.23	2.25	2.51	2.44

Notes: ***Significant at 1%; **Significant at 5%; *Significant at 10%. Standard errors are in parentheses. Success is the dependent variable (1=Success; 0=Failure).

Hypotheses 2a and 2b are tested in Models 3 and 4. We can observe that the estimated coefficient on Dev is positive and significant in the two models ($\beta_{14} = 0.536$ and $\beta_{14} = 0.582$, respectively). In addition, the coefficient on the interaction term between Risk and Dev is also positive and significant ($\beta_{15} = 0.139$). These results mean that the degree of development of the host country where the PPP project is located positively affects its success. In addition, the positive effect on PPPs' performance of transferring risk to the private sector seems to be more intense under better economic environments (Figure 4 in the appendix shows a graphical analysis of this interaction effect). Thus, we cannot reject hypotheses 2a and 2b.

These results are in line with previous findings, where a higher degree of development is positively related to the availability of factors required for the productive activity, such as basic infrastructures or qualified workforce, among others. A sufficient level of endowment for these factors can contribute to successfully management of PPP projects (Fleta et al., 2019). More developed countries are characterized by a more stable macroeconomic environment, which has been highlighted in academic literature as one of the main issues that attract or repel money from private investors. Galilea and Medda (2010) find that an economic environment characterized by high levels of volatility negatively affects PPPs' success. Grilo et al. (2005) highlight that the engagement of private companies in long-term investments in PPP infrastructure projects largely depends on the economic stability of the country where the project is deployed. Hammami et al. (2006) point out that PPPs are more usual in environments with less inflation and more stable exchange rates, and that more stable macroeconomic environments attract more private investment. In the same vein, Mota and Moreira (2015) find that economic stability is an important factor for the success of PPP projects and for the involvement of the private sector. Moreover, more developed countries

present more efficient financial markets. This is another economic feature that has been highlighted as one of the most relevant key drivers for PPPs in academic literature (Li et al., 2005).

Constraints in financial markets have a negative impact on private sector involvement in PPP projects (Burger et al., 2009; Connolly and Wall, 2011). Connolly and Wall (2011) document how the bank collapse due to the global financial crisis in 2009 led to liquidity restrictions in debt markets, hindering the involvement of private companies in PPP projects. A lack of funding not only prevents new projects from being established, but also has negative consequences for those that are already under way. Connolly and Wall (2011) find that a lack of funding generates delays and increases borrowing costs, hurting the VfM of these projects. Furthermore, when funds are not available from traditional sources, it is necessary to resort to foreign banks, leading to higher exposure to exchange rate risks or the public sector assuming greater responsibility in this area, providing funds to the project either directly or through public financial institutions, which “makes a mockery of the private in PPP and completely undermines the claims of its proponents that it would spread the cost of projects as well as transfer the risk of borrowing away from the state and on to private firms” (Connolly and Wall, 2011, p. 540).

Table 4 presents the results for models testing hypothesis 3a. Given the high correlation between the different variables from the WGI database (see Table 2), and following previous literature (Percoco, 2014; Wang et al., 2019), we include each of them separately in the estimations. These results are shown in Models 5–10. We can observe that the Wald χ^2 and likelihood ratio test comparing the nested model and VIF analysis show the convenience of the models proposed, and the coefficients of control variables remain similar to those obtained in the base model and Models 2–4. This shows the consistency of our previous

results. With regard to the coefficients of the WGI variables, five of them are positive and only one is negative. However, three of the indicators display positive and significant results, as expected, these being the indicators for control of corruption (Model 5; $\beta_{14} = 1.335$), regulatory quality (Model 8; $\beta_{14} = 0.669$) and rule of law (Model 9; $\beta_{14} = 0.920$). These results mean that better records on these issues are positively related to the likelihood of PPPs' success. Thus, we cannot reject H3a, at least for the institutional features covered by the indicators obtaining significant coefficients.

The results are in line with others where the institutional environment where the PPP occurs is an important driver for this type of project. High levels of corruption in the host countries where projects are deployed are linked with a high likelihood of failure (Jimenez et al., 2017). In the same vein, Percoco (2014) concludes that private investment in PPPs in the transportation sector is negatively affected by corruption. The author explains that economies with high levels of corruption have problems attracting foreign direct investment, and that corruption supposes additional transaction costs that lead to efficiency losses due to an inappropriate allocation of resources. Grilo et al. (2005) assert that institutional quality and the soundness of legal and regulatory frameworks in the host country have an important impact on private sector engagement in long-term investments in infrastructure PPPs. Similar results are obtained by Percoco (2014) with regard to private involvement in the transportation sector. Zhang (2005) highlights the relevance of a legal and regulatory framework to create an environment able to attract private investors to PPP projects. Panayides et al. (2015) also find that regulatory quality and ease of enforcing contracts are important determinants for port PPPs' success.

Table 5 presents the results from models testing hypothesis 3b. For each of the WGI variables, we build interaction terms by interacting them with the risk ranking index. Results

are reported in Models 11–16. For the sake of brevity, we only report results of the coefficients relevant to the hypothesis. As in the previous models, the Wald χ^2 and likelihood ratio test compared with the logit and VIF analysis show the convenience of the models proposed. Results of risk and WGI variables are consistent with those achieved in previous models.

Focusing on the coefficients from interaction terms, we observe that three out of six are significant; however, they are not consistent in sign (Figures 5, 6 and 7 in the appendix show a graphical analysis of these interaction effects). The interaction term with the expected sign is obtained for Model 16 ($\beta_{15} = 0.216$). However, contrary to our expectations, in Models 14 and 15 the interaction terms adopt negative and significant coefficients ($\beta_{15} = -0.212$; $\beta_{15} = -0.165$). Thus, improvement of regulatory quality and rule of law moderate the positive effect on PPPs' success of transferring risk to the private sector. These results can be explained by several arguments.

Firstly, following Baker's (2016) reasoning, the improvements in the institutional environment could not affect all the PPP types, because independent regulatory structures are not frequent in transitional economies. This means that public partners would not be neutral in these markets, and so governments would change regulations to protect their interests in case of an unforeseen event. Thus, general improvement of the rule of law and regulatory quality could asymmetrically influence different PPP types, affecting the most complex ones negatively (i.e. when the risk transferred is higher).

Table 4. Multilevel logistic analysis: PPPs Success as the dependent variable. WGI indicators influence on PPPs success.

<i>Hypotheses Variables H(3a)</i>	Model 5	Model 6	Model 7	Model 8	Model 9	Model 10
CC	1.335*** (0.493)					
GE		0.174 (0.441)				
PS			0.314 (0.250)			
RQ				0.669** (0.273)		
RL					0.920** (0.413)	
VA						-0.387 (0.390)
Control Variables						
d_Energy	0.264 (0.359)	0.269 (0.356)	0.249 (0.357)	0.302 (0.355)	0.287 (0.357)	0.274 (0.357)
d_Transport	0.498 (0.367)	0.504 (0.364)	0.470 (0.364)	0.515 (0.362)	0.499 (0.364)	0.514 (0.364)
d_ITC	1.356*** (0.423)	1.341*** (0.420)	1.331*** (0.420)	1.414*** (0.420)	1.389*** (0.422)	1.337*** (0.419)
Size	-0.130** (0.055)	-0.122** (0.054)	-0.123** (0.054)	-0.139** (0.054)	-0.132** (0.055)	-0.120** (0.054)
Age	-0.100*** (0.023)	-0.085*** (0.023)	-0.086*** (0.023)	-0.106*** (0.024)	-0.105*** (0.025)	-0.085*** (0.022)
Local	0.477*** (0.183)	0.485*** (0.183)	0.495*** (0.183)	0.480*** (0.182)	0.486*** (0.183)	0.490*** (0.183)
GDP	0.239* (0.144)	0.297** (0.144)	0.318** (0.138)	0.225 (0.140)	0.228 (0.147)	0.312** (0.137)
Polconv	1.468** (0.583)	1.631*** (0.587)	1.586*** (0.580)	1.013 (0.623)	1.137* (0.624)	1.841*** (0.605)
Risk	0.225*** (0.048)	0.223*** (0.048)	0.223*** (0.048)	0.224*** (0.048)	0.221*** (0.048)	0.222*** (0.048)
Time controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Continent controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Intercept	-1.958 (3.901)	-4.557 (3.850)	-5.065 (3.584)	-2.045 (3.758)	-1.722 (4.031)	-5.336 (3.561)
Random parameters	2.451 (0.834)	2.303 (0.763)	2.345 (0.776)	2.041 (0.704)	2.423 (0.814)	2.341 (0.775)
Wald χ^2	153.04***	149.25***	149.49***	157.61***	152.51***	148.98***
LR test vs. Logit	313.04***	331.85***	333.48***	240.97***	337.18***	303.11***
Observations	6,022	6,022	6,022	6,022	6,022	6,022
Pseudo R ²	0.5569	0.5527	0.5527	0.5564	0.5561	0.5527
VIF	2.41	2.35	2.25	2.29	2.43	2.62

Notes: ***Significant at 1%; **Significant at 5%; *Significant at 10%. Standard errors are in parentheses. Success is the dependent variable (0=Failure; 1=Success).

Table 5. Multilevel logistic analysis: PPPs Success as the dependent variable. Interaction terms between WGI and Risk.

<i>Hypotheses Variables H(3b)</i>	Model 11	Model 12	Model 13	Model 14	Model 15	Model 16
Risk	0.223*** (0.048)					
CC	1.360*** (0.496)					
CC*Risk	-0.072 (0.121)					
Risk		0.225*** (0.048)				
GE		0.171 (0.439)				
GE*Risk		0.099 (0.107)				
Risk			0.226*** (0.048)			
PS			0.314 (0.250)			
PS*Risk			-0.045 (0.055)			
Risk				0.227*** (0.048)		
RQ				0.582** (0.280)		
RQ*Risk				-0.212*** (0.073)		
Risk					0.213*** (0.048)	
RL					0.960** (0.418)	
RL*Risk					-0.165* (0.094)	
Risk						0.193*** (0.049)
VA						-0.554 (0.384)
VA*Risk						0.216*** (0.066)
Project controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Continent controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Intercept	-0.668 (3.845)	-3.067 (3.780)	-3.522 (3.562)	0.316 (3.907)	0.110 (4.043)	-3.575 (3.412)
Random parameters	2.492 (0.849)	2.235 (0.745)	2.351 (0.776)	2.323 (0.807)	2.56 (0.864)	2.05 (0.689)
Wald χ^2	153.45***	149.46***	151.12***	161.13***	154.91***	154.32***
LR test vs. Logit	311.60***	320.24***	334.14***	236.67***	340.12***	278.70***
Observations	6,022	6,022	6,022	6,022	6,022	6,022
Pseudo R ²	0.5571	0.5525	0.5538	0.5599	0.5599	0.5534
VIF	2.39	2.32	2.21	2.25	2.41	2.57

Notes: ***Significant at 1%; **Significant at 5%; *Significant at 10%. Standard errors are in parentheses. Success is the dependent variable (1=Success; 0=Failure).

Secondly, good records on these factors could introduce rigidity, since the projects' singularities may need *ad hoc* solutions when public and private partners have to renegotiate an unforeseen event in the PPP. Thus, a sound regulatory framework and rule of law make the initial design of formal contracts and the subsequent enforcement of them easy, but reduce the scope for discretionary decisions, and where some adjustment is required in the PPP, it requires expensive and lengthy negotiations (Grilo et al., 2005). In consequence, exhaustive regulations and more contract safeguards could constrain private partners' ability to be competitive in the market (Lundqvist, 1988; Pongsiri, 2012). In fact, changes in the legal framework are one of the main risks identified in PPPs, because these projects are planned in the long term according to a specific scenario (Chan et al., 2010; Ke et al., 2010).

Finally, the negative signs of the interaction could mean that the transference of risk to the private sector in our sample could be excessive under certain circumstances. Pongsiri (2012) points out that regulatory quality enhances governments' efficiency. If the public sector is more efficient, the scope to obtain improvements in efficiency from transferring risk to the private sector is lower. Thus, good records on issues related with regulatory quality could lead the public sector to retain certain risks that would otherwise be transferred to the private partner. In this regard, Sharma (2012) finds that when governments are efficient, the public sector prefers to retain certain risks, such as those related to the building and maintenance of infrastructures, the involvement of the private sector being less. These findings are in line with other researchers, who explain that PPPs that bear high risk and are long-term may be more exposed to institutional risks, and that once these decrease, the type of PPP chosen will be less efficient (Percoco, 2014).

In fact, some authors suggest that risks related to the legal framework should fall on the public side or be shared (Li et al., 2005; Ke et al., 2010), while operational risks are generally assigned to the private party (Ng and Loosemore, 2007; Ke et al., 2010). Therefore, high levels of risk transferred to the private party, when reduced, could involve specific resources and capabilities dedicated to institutional risks that do not occur (Jin and Doloi, 2008), reducing the availability of means to face other more probable risks, decreasing margins, reducing confidence in the public partner. Thus, Thomas et al. (2003) stress that there is a tendency for the public party to outsource all the risks they can to the private party, when this could affect their success by not locating the risks with the parties most qualified to manage them. In this context, a private party may be forced by the public party to accept risk, a situation more likely to occur in PPP types, which involve more risk for the private operator. Thus, when the conditions of the institutional environments that generate risks improve, private parties that assume a lower level of risk will better match their resources and have better results.

4.2. Robustness analyses

In order to check the robustness of the results, we perform the same analyses through other variables related to the three fundamental factors of the hypotheses: risk, economic environment and institutional context. For reasons of space, we include the results related to Hypotheses 2a, 2b, 3a, and 3b for some of these new variables (Table 6). The other results are available upon request from the authors.

We use three new proxies for the risk variable. The first one is based on the four main types of PPP according to the World Bank's classification (Risk4). They encompass the twelve subtypes shown in Figure 2. The four types are management and lease contracts, brownfield projects, greenfield projects, and divestiture projects. The public sector retains more risk in the first category, and the private party takes more risk in the fourth category.

In this way, the values that can adopt the new proxy of risk range from 1 to 4, 1 being less risk taken by the private party and 4 being more. In addition, the other two proxies are built considering that the rise in the risk transferred from the public sector to the private one when moving from one PPP subtype to the next (see Figure 2) is decreasing or increasing. Thus, we apply Napierian logarithms to each value of the original scale from 1 to 12, obtaining a new risk indicator in which the rise in the risk transferred from the public sector to the private one becomes smaller (RiskL). Analogously, to transform the original scale to another representing ever-increasing increments in the risk transferred to the private party, we reverse RiskL (RiskH).

In short, the models with the new proxies for risk, testing Hypotheses 1, 2a, 2b and 3a, provide results consistent with previous ones. In addition, in the case of Hypothesis 3b, 14 of the 18 models (Models 11 to 16, with three alternative risk variables for each) present the same signs and significance as the previous results. Furthermore, the changes that occur in the other four models keep the previous coefficients' signs. Specifically, one interaction effect becomes significant, as expected (Model 12); one governance indicator variable becomes non-significant (Model 14); and the same interaction term becomes non-significant in two of the risk variables (Model 15).

With regard to the additional proxy of economic environment, we follow previous authors (Galilea and Medda, 2010; Wang et al., 2018) and use an ordinal variable that represents the degree of development of the country (according to its classification in the World Bank database) where the PPP has been introduced. This new proxy (Economic_Dev) adopts the value of 1 for low-income countries, the value of 2 for lower-middle income countries, and the value of 3 for upper-middle income countries. The new variable is measured in the models in which it appears (Model 3 – H2a and Model 4 – H2b). Table 6 shows the results with the original risk variable (Risk) and the risk in four

categories (Risk4). These outcomes show that the estimated coefficient of the new proxy of economic environment (H2a) continues to be positive but now becomes non-significant. Additionally, the interaction effect between risk and economic environment is positive and significant (H2b), and is thus consistent in sign and significance with our previous results.

For the six governance indicators representing specific features of the institutional environment, we repeat the analyses using their average as a unique variable (G_Average). Thus, we test H3a and H3b with this indicator (which could be considered as a proxy for the overall institutional context). Table 6 shows that good results in the institutional environment positively affect the success of the PPPs (H3a). On the other hand, the effect of a non-significant coefficient on the interaction between G_average and risk (H3b) seems reasonable, since the results of the disaggregated interactions had positive, negative, significant, and non-significant effects depending on the specific indicator considered (Table 5).

Table 6. Robustness analyses with alternative risk (Risk4), governance indicators (G_Average) and economic development (Economic_Dev) variables.

<i>Hypotheses Variables</i>	Model 17 (H2a)	Model 18 (H2b)	Model 19 (H2a)	Model 20 (H2b)	Model 21 (H3a)	Model 22 (H3a)	Model 23 (H3b)	Model 24 (H3b)
Risk	0.223*** (0.048)	0.234*** (0.049)			0.224*** (0.048)		0.225*** (0.048)	
Risk4			0.801*** (0.158)	0.852*** (0.163)		0.801*** (0.158)		0.810*** (0.159)
Economic_Dev.	0.418 (0.524)	0.347 (0.524)	0.420 (0.512)	0.415 (0.510)				
Risk*Economic_Dev.		0.177*** (0.059)						
Risk4*Economic_Dev.				0.481** (0.210)				
G_Average					1.011** (0.510)	0.978* (0.505)	1.038** (0.514)	0.968* (0.507)
Risk*G_Average							-0.066 (0.115)	
Risk4*G_Average								-0.360 (0.442)
<i>Control Variables</i>	Yes							
Intercept	-5.459 (3.528)	-3.204 (3.658)	-6.156* (3.467)	-3.017 (3.573)	-2.556 (3.885)	-3.381 (3.820)	-1.033 (3.846)	-1.147 (3.770)
Random parameters	2.217 (0.743)	2.191 (0.732)	2.066 (0.696)	2.034 (0.685)	2.311 (0.775)	2.168 (0.730)	2.356 (0.794)	2.207 (0.744)
Wald χ^2	149.31***	152.94***	152.31***	154.23***	152.74***	155.49***	153.47***	156.79***
LR test vs. Logit	320.82***	323.39***	293.42***	292.61***	331.22***	304.42***	330.76***	305.08***
Pseudo R ²	0.5512	0.5629	0.5535	0.5629	0.5561	0.5584	0.5568	0.5591
VIF	2.52	2.48	2.46	2.40	2.40	2.33	2.38	2.31

Notes: ***Significant at 1%; **Significant at 5%; *Significant at 10%. Standard errors are in parentheses. Success is the dependent variable (0=Failure; 1=Success). Observations 6,022.

5. Conclusions

PPPs have gained relevance in recent years and nowadays constitute a broad formula for the provision of infrastructure services. One of the main advantages of PPPs in relation to public procurement is the efficiency gained from transferring risk from the public to the private sector. In this paper, we have examined how this transfer of risks impacts on PPPs' results. We have analysed a broad sample of 6,022 projects deployed in 59 developing countries in the period 1997–2016, using multilevel models that allow us to control for countries' specificities. The results achieved demonstrate that there is a positive and significant relationship between the level of risk assumed by the private investor and the performance of PPP projects. Thus, the higher the risk transferred to the private sector, the greater the likelihood of success. In addition, we have examined how the economic and institutional environments affect these issues. We conclude that better economic environments make PPPs' success more likely and make the positive effect of transferring risk to the private partner of a PPP performance more intense. Furthermore, a sound institutional environment and, more concretely, good records on control of corruption, regulatory quality and rule of law, positively affects PPPs' success. However, better records on these two last institutional features moderate the positive effect on PPPs' performance of transference of risk to the private sector. This last result is especially interesting and highlights that although, in general terms, a good institutional environment is positively related to the likelihood of success of PPP projects, it could reduce the scope for achieving efficiency gains when transferring risk to the private partner. Excessive transference of risk from the public to the private sector when the public sector can efficiently manage some of these risks will damage the project's likelihood of success. This result means that there is no optimal risk allocation valid for all projects with similar characteristics performed through PPPs, but it depends on the

institutional environment where the PPP is performed and on the capabilities of the involved partners to manage the different types of risk.

Further research can be performed in the fields studied in this paper. A comparison of risk allocation for projects with similar characteristics but performed in environments with different levels of institutional quality could provide new insights to add to the empirical evidence provided in this paper. Thus, it could be interesting to extend the analysis to PPPs in developed countries where the economic and institutional environment could have a different impact. Moreover, the study of other environmental characteristics, such as social factors, could provide new insights. Other proxies for risk would allow separate analysis of the effect of different types of risk. Although in this research we have controlled our results by considering variables at the country and project level, it could be interesting to include variables representing characteristics of the private companies or the managers in charge of these projects. Data availability has prevented us from performing this type of control, but it could be another interesting issue to deal with in future research.

Appendix.

Figure 4. Risk and Success by economic development (higher and lower values)

Figure 5. Risk and Success by Regulatory Quality (higher and lower values)

Figure 6. Risk and Success by Rule of Law (higher and lower values)

Figure 7. Risk and Success by Voice and Accountability (higher and lower values)

This appendix provides a graphical analysis of the interaction effects. Since the variable “success” is estimated with interactions in which “risk” is present, they appear on the vertical and horizontal axes, respectively. To show the second variable interacting with risk, we project on these axes the sample split into two sets of observations, separated by the value of its median. Thus, the significant interaction of Hypothesis 2b appears in Figure 4, while Hypothesis 3b appears in Figures 5, 6, and 7 for the different governance indicators with significant interaction terms.

Firstly, it can be seen that the slopes are not parallel. This denotes a different behaviour between both groups. For the signs, the interactions of risk with the economic environment (Model 4, Figure 4) and with the institutional context for the voice and accountability indicator (Model 16, Figure 7) are positive. Thus, in Figure 4, the positive effect of increasing the risk transferred to the private partner upon PPPs’ success is greater for the set of observations formed by the higher values of economic development. For this reason, the slope for the observations with the higher values (solid line) is greater than the slope for the observations with lower values (dashed line). The reasoning is analogous for Figure 7.

In contrast, the risk interactions with the institutional variables of regulatory quality (Model 14, Figure 5) and rule of law (Model 15, Figure 6) present negative coefficients. This means that, for example for Figure 5, the positive effect of raising the risk transferred to the private partner upon PPPs’ success is less intense for the set of observations formed by the higher values of regulatory quality. For this reason, the (solid) line that represents this relationship has less of a slope compared with the (dashed) line depicting the lower regulatory quality values. The reasoning is analogous for Figure 6.

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